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Search for dark matter induced event rate modulation in DarkSide-50 ionization signal

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Abstract

The DarkSide-50 experiment has performed a direct dark matter search using a dual-phase argon time projection chamber at the Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso (LNGS). Based solely on the ionization signal, it has set the most stringent exclusion limits for several low-mass dark matter candidates. Dark matter can also be searched for in a model-independent way exploiting the annual dark matter event rate modulation. In this contribution, we present the first search of such an event rate modulation with argon. No significant signature comparable with dark matter is observed in the electron recoil equivalent energy range above 0.04 keV_{ee} , the lowest energy threshold ever proved in an annual dark matter modulation search.

1 Introduction

Dark matter induced event rate in terrestrial detectors is expected to show an annual modulation as a result of the combined effect of Earth's rotation around the Sun and the galactic center. The DAMA/LIBRA experiment, as well as its pioneer DAMA/NaI, claimed the detection of such a signature in their NaI crystal detector in the keV electron recoil equivalent (keV_{ee}) region over more than 20 years [1, 2], while the other experiments yet confirm it [3–7]. The interpretation of the positive claim with the Weakly Interacting Massive Particle (WIMP) hypothesis is facing challenges due to the null detection of WIMP-induced nuclear recoil signals in other experiments [7–15]. An independent approach to test the claim can be offered by searching for the modulation with other detectors which have different target materials, background sources, energy resolution, and experimental sites.

The DarkSide-50 detector is a liquid argon (LAr) time projection chamber (TPC) located at the Laboratori Nazionali del Gran Sasso (LNGS), recently demonstrated an unprecedented sensitivity in search for low-mass dark matter by looking for an event excess in the ionization signal spectrum with respect to the background model above 0.06 keV_{ee} [16–19]. Here, we present for the first time the search for the annual rate modulation of events down to 0.04 keV_{ee} , the lowest energy threshold ever achieved in such searches, using the ionization signal of the DarkSide-50.

2 Detector

The TPC has a cylindrical active mass of $(46.4 \pm 0.7) \text{ kg}$ of low-radioactivity argon extracted from an underground source (UAr). Two arrays of nineteen 3-in. photomultiplier tubes (PMTs) sit at the top and bottom. They detect scintillation (S1) and electroluminescence (S2) light pulses induced from particle interacting in the liquid bulk. The latter is produced by ionization electrons that are drifted in gaseous argon at the top of the TPC by a 200 V/cm electric field in the active region, F_d . The average number of S2 per ionization electron, g_2 , is measured to be (23 ± 1) photoelectron/ e^- around the center of the TPC.

The trigger is fired upon a coincidence of at least two PMTs above 0.6 photoelectron within 100 ns . Pulses within the acquired data is reconstructed offline. The combined efficiency of the trigger and the pulse reconstruction becomes essentially 100% at $1.3 e^-$ [20], much below our energy threshold of $3 e^-$.

3 Dataset

The data used in this work was taken from August 2015 to February 2018. During this period, we conducted several detector calibration campaigns with radioactive sources, which accounted for approximately 25% of the total duration. Apart from that, the data taking was not interrupted significantly; the total livetime in this analysis is 693.3 d without a break longer than 30 d .

A critical aspect of this analysis is long-term stability of the detector performance. The two parameters whose fluctuations may potentially have a high impact are F_d and g_2 , as they directly change the observed S2 light yield per unit energy deposition. The stability of F_d is monitored via the drift time (i.e. the time difference between S1 and S2) of events at the very bottom of the TPC. The maximum fluctuation of F_d is evaluated to be less than 0.01% , too small to affect the ionization response. Based on the S2/S1 ratio for events above the energy region of interest ($0.04\text{--}21 \text{ keV}_{ee}$), g_2 varies at most by 0.5% . We found by pseudo experiments that

the impact from such instability is negligible compared to the statistical fluctuations in our dataset.

We follow the exactly the same event selection criteria as that used in the preceding low-mass dark matter searches [16]. It selects single-scatter (i.e., with a single S2 pulse), low energy events after a veto of 20 ms for each trigger. It then removes pileup pulses, surface α events, and events reconstructed at outer ~ 7 cm thick cylindrical shell of the TPC to suppress background events. In order to reject the so-called spurious electron (SE) background, we define the energy threshold to be $3 e^-$.

4 Result

The annual modulation signal is searched for using the time-dependent event rate in every 7 d. The time evolution of background events are modeled by the combination of a set of decaying exponentials (^{37}Ar (half-life of 35.0 d), ^{85}Kr (10.8 yr), ^{60}Co (5.27 yr), and ^{54}Mn (312.1 d)) and a constant term (dominated by ^{39}Ar (268 yr)). The energy spectrum of each component is generated with the **Geant-4** Monte Carlo code. The activities of the short-decayed isotopes are determined by either *in situ* measurements with DarkSide-50 (^{37}Ar and ^{85}Kr) or an extensive materials screening campaign to characterize the trace radioactivity content of every detector component (^{60}Co and ^{54}Mn). The statistical significance of a possible modulation signal is assessed by a binned likelihood fit with the following model,

$$f(t) = A_\chi \cos\left(\frac{t - \phi}{T/2\pi}\right) + \sum_l \frac{A_l}{\tau_l} e^{-t/\tau_l} + C \quad (1)$$

$(l = ^{37}\text{Ar}, ^{85}\text{Kr}, ^{54}\text{Mn}, ^{60}\text{Co}),$

where A_χ is the amplitude of the modulation term of the signal, ϕ the phase, and T the period fixed to 1 yr. The constant term C is the sum of the time-averaged signal component and long-lived background. A_l and τ_l are the amplitude and the decay constant, respectively, of the short-decayed component l . Figure 1 shows the best fit values of (A_χ, ϕ) and the associated 68% and 95% contours for $4\text{--}41 e^-$ (corresponding to $0.06\text{--}2 \text{ keV}_{ee}$) and $41\text{--}68 e^-$ ($2\text{--}6 \text{ keV}_{ee}$). The likelihood includes nuisance parameters accounting for the uncertainties on the amplitudes of the short-decayed backgrounds, on the fiducial volume, on the theoretical calculation of β -decay spectrum, and on the ionization response of LAr.

Additional constraints on the modulation amplitude are obtained by simultaneously fitting the event timestamps and energies after fixing both the period (1 yr) and the phase (maximum at June 2nd) to those expected from dark matter. This approach does not require any assumption on the SE rate and thus allows the range to be extended down to $3 e^-$. The contamination of the SE in $3\text{--}4 e^-$ is accounted by anchoring its time variation to that of events below $3 e^-$, selected in coincidence with the previous event, largely dominated by SE. The chosen bin width along the energy axis is 0.02 keV_{ee} below 0.06 keV_{ee} , 0.25 keV_{ee} below 1 keV_{ee} , 1 keV_{ee} up to 6 keV_{ee} , and 2 keV_{ee} elsewhere, starting from 0.04 keV_{ee} ($3 e^-$). Figure 2 shows the best-fitted amplitude as a function of the energy, together with the 1- and 2- σ significance coverages, as derived with background-only Monte Carlo datasets.

Finally, in order to look for a sinusoidal signal with any period, we perform a Lomb-Scargle periodogram [21] analysis. We apply the periodogram to the data residual after the subtraction of the background-only fit result for the $4\text{--}41 e^-$ and $41\text{--}68 e^-$ ranges. The false alarm probability is calculated with the Bootstrap

Figure 1: Best fit parameters in (A_χ, ϕ) space from the likelihood analysis with the fixed period of 1 yr. The vertical dotted line represents the phase of the dark matter signal expected from the standard halo model.

method [21] and used to assess the significance of the sinusoidal signals. As shown in Fig 3, no significant modulation signal is observed.

5 Conclusion

We searched for dark matter annual modulation using the DarkSide-50 data. Utilizing the ionization signal only, we probed the energy range down to 0.04 keV_{ee} ($3 e^-$), the lowest energy threshold ever achieved in such a search. At the same time, we use argon as the target material of the modulation search for the first time. In none of the analyzed intervals, a modulation signal was observed. The significance of this result is not sufficient to confirm or reject the DAMA/LIBRA observation. This achievement was accomplished by the stability of the DarkSide-50 TPC over nearly three years of operation, the accuracy of the background model, and the low-energy threshold achieved. It demonstrates a promising view of such search in future experiments which will have larger mass, longer exposure time, and lower background level.

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Figure 2: Best fit amplitude of the modulation signal as a function of N_e . The green and yellow bands represent the expected 1σ and 2σ statistical fluctuations derived by background-only Monte Carlo samples.

Figure 3: Observed sinusoidal signal strengths from the Lomb-Scargle periodogram as a function of its period.

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